

The Historical Development of Sociology of Literature

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8300475

Abstract

The sociology of literature has been a marginal area in the discipline of sociology. Many scholars writing on the sociology of literature see the area as a sideline and produce only a single book or article on the subject. This has exacerbated the lack of structure in the development of the field. None of the 'founding fathers' of sociology produced a detailed study of literature, but they did develop ideas that were subsequently applied to literature by others. Although sociological approach to the study of literature has long and distinguished history from Plato onwards, it has gained its special place in the history of critical theory in the late twentieth century in the hands of Lucien Goldman, Leo Lowenthal, Robert Escarpit, Alan Swingwood, Diana Laurenson, John Hall and the several social thinkers and critics. In order to understand the development of the sociological approach to the study of literature, it is necessary to see the historical development of this approach through the contribution of the social critics and scholars. In this article an attempt has been made to focus the relationship between sociology and literature and the major contributors who tried to develop the sociological approach to the study of literature.

Key Words: Literature, Society, sociology, sociology of literature, Historical development of sociology of literature.

Introduction

The sociology of literature has been a marginal area in the discipline of sociology. Many scholars writing on the sociology of literature see the area as a sideline and produce only a single book or article on the subject.

This has exacerbated the lack of structure in the development of the field. As J.H.Mueller pointed out, sociologists in the United States have paid little attention to literature and art; they, like other social scientists, have focused primarily on the instrumental aspects of social life (Mueller, 1935) (Mueller, 1938). What is new, however, is the relative legitimacy of the study of literature within the discipline of sociology. This is due both to the increasing interest in culture in sociology after years of marginalization and to the increasing influence of cultural studies on sociology and throughout the academy. A broader interest in and acceptance of cultural sociology has meant that the types of research questions and methods common to sociological studies of literature are now more widely accepted within the field. Sociology has extended its methodological boundaries in response to both attacks on the dominance of positivism and the rising power of alternative stances suggested by postmodernism. At the same time, changes in the goals, and sometimes the methods, of studying literature sociologically have moved the area closer to what is still the mainstream of the discipline. Thus the sociology of literature has benefited from a twofold movement in which (1) sociology as a discipline has become more interested in and accepting of research questions pertaining to meaning and employing qualitative methods; and (2) the sociology of literature has evolved in the direction of more mainstream sociological areas through the merging of quantitative with qualitative methods and of empirical with hermeneutic research questions¹. In this article an attempt has been made to focus the relationship between sociology and literature and the major contributors who tried to develop the sociological approach to the study of literature.

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¹ From "Literature and Society", *Encyclopedia of Sociology*, Retrieved on 30 Nov, 2015, from <http://www.encyclopedia.com/article-1G2-3404400216/literature-and-society.html>

Literature & Society

The relationship between literature and society has been very close and inseparable from the very beginning. Defining literature is a challenging and a difficult task. Literature is a term used to describe written or spoken material. Broadly speaking, 'literature' is most commonly used to refer to works of the creative imagination, including works of poetry, drama, fiction, and nonfiction.

Literature is a reflection of the society is a fact that has been widely acknowledged. Literature, as an imitation of human action, often presents a picture of what people think, say and do in the society. In literature, we find stories designed to portray human life and action through some characters who, by their words, action and reaction, convey certain messages for the purpose of education, information and entertainment. What writers of literature do is to transport the real-life events in their society into fiction and present it to the society as a mirror with which people can look at themselves and make amends where necessary. We all know that literature mirrors society. What happens in a society is reflected in literary works in one form or another.

Sociology and Its Relationship with Literature:

While introducing the theoretical premises of the sociology of literature, it is necessary to discuss the nature and scope of both sociology and literature. Generally, 'sociology' is defined as the scientific study of society, more specifically human society. Sociology as an independent discipline of social science emerged only around the middle of the eighteenth century. The term sociology was coined by Auguste Comte, a French philosopher, in his work *Positive Philosophy* in 1839. The word 'Sociology' is derived from the Latin word *societus* meaning 'society' and the Greek word *logos* meaning 'study or science'.

The etymological meaning of 'sociology' is thus the 'science of society'. According to Gisbert (Gisbert, 2010) sociology is generally defined as 'the science of society'. W.F. Ogburn stated that, Sociology is a body of learning about society. It is a description of ways to make society better. It is social ethics, a social philosophy. Generally, however, it is defined as a science of society². According to Alan Swingewood (Swingewood, 1972) ,Sociology is essentially the scientific, objective study of man in society, the study of social institutions and of social processes; it seeks to answer the question how society is possible, how it works, why it persists. In the *Blackwell Dictionary of Sociology*³, sociology is defined as ' the study of social life and behavior, especially in relation to social system, how they work, how they change, the consequences they produce, and their complex relation to people's lives'.

All the above definitions emphasize that 'sociology' is the scientific study of man and his society, social actions and interactions, social institutions and processes, and the structure and system of society. Sociology is really a long discourse about human society that seeks to answer the questions such as; how society is possible, how it works and why it persists. Like Comte, Herbert Spencer (1820-1903) contributed a great deal to the establishment of sociology as a systematic discipline. In his *Principles of Sociology* (1877), Spencer explained the major fields of sociology and laid emphasis on the sociological study of community, family, social control, politics and industry. He also mentioned the sociological study of art and aesthetics. His emphasis is mainly on the inter-relations of the different elements and factors of the society. Karl

Marx (1818-1883), Emile Durkheim (1858-1917) and Max Weber (1864-1920) also contributed to the establishment of sociology as a systematic and scientific discipline. Karl Marx placed his emphasis

² Cited in Bhushan Bidya & Sachdeva D.R.(2012): *Fundamentals of Sociology*; Pearson; Delhi, Chennai, Chandigarh.

³ Johnson Allan G.(2000): *The Blackwell Dictionary of Sociology*; 2nd Edition; Blackwell Publishing;USA,UK.

on the economic base of society. According to him, economic base influences the general character of all other aspects of culture and social structure. Emile Durkheim analyzed social life in terms of social facts and claimed that social facts are nothing but collective ways of thinking and feeling about society. For Max Weber, the individual is the base unit of society. He devoted much of his efforts to expound a special method called the method of understanding (*verstehen*) for the study of social phenomena. In addition to these founding fathers, a large number of modern sociologists and thinkers contribute significantly to explain the nature of sociology. Besides these thinkers, the French Revolution, the Industrial Revolution and the intellectual ideologies such as individualism, socialism, positivism, humanitarianism, colonialism, and the growth and developments in modern natural sciences contribute to the emergence of 'sociology'. However, the credit for establishing sociology as an independent discipline goes to August Comte, Herbert Spencer, Karl Marx, Durkheim and Max Weber who took a leading role in making sociology a scientific discipline of social science. But none of the 'founding fathers' of sociology produced a detailed study of literature, but they did develop ideas that were subsequently applied to literature by others.

Sociology as the science of social relations studies the society and gets its subject matter from different sources, literature being one of them. As a social product, literature reflects human society, the human relation and the world in which we live, interact and move. Literature, like sociology, critically examines the realistic picture of human life. So it has been called as the mirror and controller of the society. Sociology tries to study the literary facts and their impact on social relations. Today, sociology is firmly established as a distinctive discipline. Unlike other social sciences, it is interested in almost all aspects of man's social life. The new generation of thinkers and scholars has invented new concepts and methods of sociological research. As a result, we get new branches of sociology that is Sociology of literature.

Sociology of literature

The sociology of literature is a specialized area of study which focuses its attention upon the relation between a literary work and the social structure in which it is created. As there is a reciprocal relationship between a literary phenomena and social structure, sociological study of literature proves very useful to understand the socioeconomic situations, political issues, the world view and creativity of the writers, the system of the social and political organizations, the relations between certain thoughts and cultural configurations in which they occur and determinants of a literary work. Sociology of literature studies literature for understanding society. It studies the social production of literature and its social implications. Like sociology, literature too is pre-eminently concerned with man's social world, his adaptation to it and his desire to change it. In fact, man and his society is the material out of which literature is constructed. So, literature is regarded as the expression or representation of human life through the medium of social creation viz. language. According to W. H. Hudson (Hudson, 1958) "literature is a vital record of what men have seen in life, what they have experienced of it, what they have thought and felt about those aspects of it which have the most immediate and enduring interest for all of us. It is thus fundamentally an expression of life through the medium of language". The society and individuals are thus the materials of literature. The outer world gets transformed within author's mind and heart and these transformed elements become reality in literature. Literature and society are always dependent on each other. The most important reason of this interdependent relationship is that literature is the social institution and it uses the medium of language, a social creation. It depicts life and life is a social reality. In short, the base of both sociology and literature is alike and their stability is conditioned by the major social institutions. The changes in the form and content of literature are caused by the changes in the society and the society changes due to the current of fresh and new ideas provided by

literary works. The contemporary literature has become more reader centered and the emphasis is laid upon economic, material and environmental conditions of man. Previously, it was believed that the philosophical doctrines supply materials to literature but in the modern age it is considered as an account of the changes in the social structure caused by industrialism, capitalism, communism and totalitarianism. It has become more materialistic in approach. It reveals human actions in the contexts of economic factors, especially on the mode of production. It also experiments with the surroundings on human mind. The early literature laid emphasis on ethics and believed in the needs of reforming society, but with the development of new scientific ideas, the shape of literature is changed by giving importance to man and his environment. As a result social order is at the center in modern literature. The sociology of literature studies this correlation between literature and sociology. The great literary works contain social, political, environmental, religious, economic and domestic values of the day. The form and style of literature change with the changes in the temper of the age and society. So literature is regarded as the expression of society. The relationship between literature and society is a two way. It influences society and gets influenced by the society. Therefore its importance cannot be ignored while judging literature.

The Sociology of Literature: Historical Development

None of the 'founding fathers' of sociology produced a detailed study of literature, but they did develop ideas that were subsequently applied to literature by others. Although sociological approach to the study of literature has long and distinguished history from Plato onwards, it has gained its special place in the history of critical theory in the late twentieth century in the hands of Lucien Goldman, Leo Lowenthal, Robert Escarpit, Alan Swingwood, Diana Laurensen John Hall and the several social thinkers and critics. In order to understand the development of the

sociological approach to the study of literature, it is necessary to see the historical development of this approach through the contribution of the social critics and scholars. The Major among them are as follows.

Karl Marx and Frederick Engels: Both Marx and Engels analyze literature in terms of material foundations. They thought that the essence, the nature and function of art and literature could be understood by relating it to the prevailing social conditions and by analyzing the social system as the whole. Literature and art, as considered by them, are forms of social consciousness and social change is bound to create changes in literature and art. They also state that the nature and mode of economic production create social relations in which men enter to form class relations and these class relations become the ideology of the society. Literature tries to stabilize this ideology.

Hippolyte Taine: Hippolyte Taine, who for the first time tried to provide a systematic formula of 'race, milieu and moment' to comprehend and analyze literature in the context of the sociological approach to the study of literature, is regarded as the father of the sociology of literature. His *History of English Literature* (1871) contains an awareness of the basic problems which face any literary sociology. Taine regards literature not as the expression of personality, as explained by the romanticists, but the collective expression of society embodying the spirit of the age and formative factors behind the emergence of this expression are 'race, milieu and moment'. The interaction of this triad produces a speculative mental structure which leads to the development of the 'general ideas which find expression in great art and literature'⁴.

⁴ Jadhav , Dr. Arun Murlidhar (May 2014): The Historical Development of the Sociological Approach to the Study of Literature, *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT*, May, 2014 Vol 3 Issue 5; Retrieved on 30 Nov, 2015, from <http://www.ijird.com/index.php/ijird/article/viewFile/50325/40998>

George Luckacs: An important first step in the sociology of literature was taken by Georg Lukács's *The Theory of the Novel*, first published in German in 1916, in the *Zeitschrift für Aesthetik und Allgemeine Kunstwissenschaft*⁵. The major contributions of George Luckacs in the history of the sociology of literature are *The Meaning of Contemporary Realism* (1963), *The Historical Novel* (1963), *Writer and Critic* (1970), *The Theory of the Novel* (1971), and *Studies in European realism* (1972).

Lucian Goldman

Goldman's contribution in the history of the sociology of literature lies in the introduction of dialectical materialism, the sophisticated method of linking art and society. His essay "The Sociology of Literature: Status and Problems of Method" presents some observations of genetic structuralism. According to him, the first general observation on which genetic structuralist thought based is that 'all reflection on the human sciences is made not from without but from within society'. The second basic idea of genetic sociology is that human facts are responses of an individual or collective subject. He further points out that the essential relationship between the life of society and literary creation is not concerned with the content of these two sectors of human reality but only with the mental structures and those mental structures are not individual phenomena but social phenomena (Goldman, 1967). His major contributions in the field of the sociology of literature are: *The Hidden God* (1956), *Towards a Sociology of Novel* (1964), *The Sociology of Literature: Status and Problems of Method* (1967), *Cultural Creation in Modern Society* (1976), and *Method in the Sociology of Literature* (1981).

The Frankfurt School

⁵ Sociology of literature, From Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia, Retrieved on 28 Nov, 2015, from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sociology_of_literature

Founded in 1923, the Institute for Social Research at the University of Frankfurt developed a distinctive kind of 'critical sociology' indebted to Marx, Weber and Freud. Leading Frankfurt School critics who worked on literature included Adorno, Walter Benjamin and Leo Löwenthal. Adorno's *Notes to Literature*, Benjamin's *The Origin of German Tragic Drama* and Löwenthal's *Literature and the Image of Man* were each influential studies in the sociology of literature. Adorno's *Notes to Literature* is a collection of essays, the most influential of which is probably 'On Lyric Poetry and Society'. It argued that poetic thought is a reaction against the commodification and reification of modern life. Habermas succeeded Adorno to the Chair of Sociology and Philosophy at Frankfurt. Habermas's first major work, *Strukturwandel der Öffentlichkeit* was published in German in 1962, and in English translation as *The Structural Transformation of the Public Sphere* in 1989. It attempted to explain the socio-historical emergence of middleclass public opinion in the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries. Developing a new kind of institutional sociology of literature, it argued that the public sphere had been organised around literary salons in France, learned and literary societies in Germany, and coffee houses in England⁶. Löwenthal was a German-Jewish sociologist usually associated with the Frankfurt School. He became a leading expert of the sociology of literature and mass culture after joining the Institute for Social Research in 1926. He, then, conducted seminar on the sociology of literature and wrote essays and books for the sociological study of literature. The notable among them are: *Literature and the Image of Man* (1957) and *Literature, Popular Culture, and Society* (1961).

Bourdieu

Bourdieu was Professor of Sociology at the Collège de France and Director of the Centre de Sociologie Européenne. His first major

⁶ "Sociology of literature", From Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia, Retrieved on 28 Nov, 2015, from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sociology_of_literature

contribution to the sociology of literature (and other arts) was *La Distinction*, published in French in 1979 and in English translation in 1984. It is based on detailed sociological surveys and ethnographic observation of the social distribution of cultural preferences.

Some Other Modern Critics

The most important work and the landmark in the history of the Sociology of Literature is John Hall's 'The Sociology of Literature' (1979). In it John Hall explains in detail the several approaches and methods of the sociology of literature, the major determinants of literature, the sociology of the writer and the role of the reading public in the creation and success of a literary work. Like Hall, Raymond Williams' *The Long Revolution* (1961), M. C. Albrecht's *The Sociology of Art and Literature* (1970), Levin Schucking's *The Sociology of Literary Taste* (1941) Elizabeth and Tom Burns eds. *Sociology of Literature and Drama: Selected Readings* (1973), and the issues of *Critical Inquiry* Vol. 14 (Spring, 1988) and *International Social Science Journal*, Vol. XIX, No. 4, ed. Peter Lengyel, UNESCO, contributed greatly in the development of the theoretical perspectives of the sociology of literature⁷. There are the diverse views about the nature, areas, methods and approaches of the sociology of literature in different countries. For instance, in the departments of sociology in American universities, the sociology of literature has deliberately adopted an empirical approach. This approach lays emphasis on the case studies of particular literary institutions such as publications, booksellers, journals etc. Like contemporary critical theories, this empirical approach ignores the social context of literature and emphasizes the determinant of literary works. However, the European school of sociology of literature

⁷ Jadhav, Dr. Arun Murlidhar: "The Historical Development of the Sociological Approach to the Study of Literature", *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*, May, 2014 Vol 3 Issue 5; Retrieved on 30 Nov, 2015, from <http://www.ijird.com/index.php/ijird/article/viewFile/50325/40998>

encompasses a broader range of humanistic understanding and facilitates the interdisciplinary perspective that is essential to any sociological analysis of literature.

Conclusion

Sociology is an all encompassing discipline that studies social life in its totality. Sociology is concerned with the study of social relationships. Sociology provides a critique of society. With the passage of time, sociology has grown, like other social sciences and a host of sub disciplines have arisen. Sociology of Literature is one of them. And, so, it is no longer possible for a single scholar to develop an encyclopedic contribution. As Durkheim said in his seminal essay, "Sociologie et sciences sociales", "...it is impossible for a sociologist to possess encyclopaedic knowledge of his science; but each scholar must attach himself to a special order of problems unless he wishes to be content with very general and vague views"⁸ Durkheim divided the field of Sociology into three parts: Social Morphology, Social Physiology, and General Sociology. We may say that, as per Durkheim's division of the field of Sociology, the Sociology of Literature falls within the scope of Aesthetic Sociology. The International Sociological Association has 55 Research Committees. We may place Sociology of Literature within RC 14 (Sociology of Knowledge, Communication and Culture).

Great literary figures, like Victor Hugo, Charles Dickens, Leo Tolstoy, Maxim Gorky, Rabindranath Tagore, Anatole France, Romain Rolland, Ernest Hemingway, Pearl Buck, Arundhati Roy, Jhumpa Lahiri, etc., had deep social insights. That is why their works have become classics. Victor Hugo's *Les Misérables* is a severe critic of the class divided society of France in the nineteenth century. Hugo depicts how a petty bread thief is transformed into a criminal, how women abandoned by their lovers are forced to become prostitutes, how families are ruined by the anomic society that France was in the

⁸ Emile Durkheim: "Sociology and the Social Sciences" in Kenneth Thompson ed. *Readings from Emile Durkheim*, Routledge, London & New York 1985, p.p. 26

nineteenth century. *Les Miserables* highlights a society which fails to provide justice to people. That apart, Hugo wrote many other novels, like *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, *Toilers of the Sea*, *The Man Who Laughs*, etc. In a similar vein, Charles Dickens criticized 19th century English and European society through a series of novels. *A Tale of Two Cities*, for example, is a story of crime, scapegoating revenge, and sacrifice in the backdrop of the French revolution. *Oliver Twist* is a story of an orphan boy, born in a workhouse. Through such other novels as, *Great Expectations*, *Hard Times*, *Nicholas Nickleby*, *David Copperfield*, etc. Dickens made a trenchant criticism of 19th century English society which differed little from Victor Hugo's France. Another important 19th century writer was Leo Tolstoy. His novels, like *War and Peace*, *Resurrection*, *Anna Karenina*, Youth and short novels, like *Kreutzer Sonata*, Tolstoy criticised 19th century Russian and European society. *War and Peace*, for example, is a novel set in the context of Russia's struggle against Napoleon. *Resurrection* is a telling comment on contemporary Russian society seen through the eyes of a nobleman. On one hand the aristocracy spend their time in luxury and idle debauchery while the poor are beaten tortured, and imprisoned often for crimes they did not commit. Gorky's novel, *Mother*, depicts the situation in Russia at the time of the 1905 revolution.

Indian writers have criticized their own society. We may mention, in this connection, *Kamalakanter Daptar* by Bankim Chandra Chattopadhyay, which criticised the many ills of 19th century Indian society through the writings of an opium eater, Kamalakanta. Rabindranath Tagore's novels, short stories and plays still have relevance in contemporary India. His short story, "Dena Paona" is a severe indictment of the dowry system in India. Tagore's dance drama, *Balmiki Pratibha*, which he wrote and acted in his youth, has been used in 21st century Bengal as a cultural therapy to reform prisoners and make them fit for social life. Another dance drama, *Tasher Desh*, ridiculed the Roy's nonsense verses were actually satires of contemporary society and

polity. His rhyme, "Ekushe Ain, for example, ridicules the legal system in colonial India. Sarat Chandra Chattopadhyay's novel, *Pather Dabi*, so greatly influenced the freedom movement that the colonial authorities banned it.

Contemporary Indian writers, like Arundhati Ray and Jhumpa Lahiri, have greatly influenced the reading public. Arundhati Ray's *The God of Small Things*, shows how the lives of two fraternal twins are destroyed by "love laws". The book brought her international fame. Since then Arundhati has become an activist. Jhumpa Lahiri's *The Interpreter of Maladies*, contains short stories depicting the lives of Indians and Indian Americans, as they try to adjust to a new culture. *The Namesake*, is the story of an Indian American youth who faces an identity crisis. Though his parents are Bengalis, he tries to become an American. These are only some examples of literary works which have greatly influenced society.

To conclude, the sociology of literature is an outcome of the complementary relationship between literature and society. It is the sociology of literature that lays emphasis on the study of the social contexts and the social determinants of literature. The scope of sociology will be better understood in the light of its relationship with literature and with all other disciplines concerned with the social life of man. We have seen that many literary figures severely criticised their societies through their literary works. At the same time, scholars have, throughout the history of sociology, contributed to the Sociology of Literature. Nevertheless, the field remains wide open and many budding sociologists may take up sociology of literature as their area of study.

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